

PRAGMATICS AND ACTIVITY EVALUATION IN TEACHING

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Annotation: In this article the author discusses about the importance of pragmatics and introduces an activity to apply for the class. Furthermore, the author identifies both advantages and disadvantages of the activity. The readers may gain knowledge on the usage of the activity and theoretical issues invited by scientists Celce-Murcia

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Pragmatics is a part of linguistics along with semantics, but they aim at different objectives: semantics deals with the meaning of the words, while the other's goal is to use the language at various contexts. Through semantics we find out what the word say about, while pragmatics helps us to know the internal meaning of the utterance. According to Cohen, goals are achieved with not just words, but how the words are said and who says them. A linguist J.L. Austin states that “To speak is to act”, thus pragmatics contains speech acts that identify in which way the speech is used. It can be of various types: complaints, apology, request, compliment, refusal, thanking, offering and so on.

When it comes to the activity, I consider the activity should be well-organized, deeply thought and meet with its objectives and goals, such as being able to identify contextual factors, level of formality and the effect of behavior. For instance, the activity PPP (preparation, presentation and product). This activity is intended for 45 minutes to organize and it has several advantages. First, the activity goes under two

stages which helps the learners to understand and consolidate what they have learned. For the first time they get aware of the context, while the next time they can feel free about what they should do and concentrate better. Next, in this activity you can observe the difference in the level of formality since initially, the conversation was between an employee and an employer, while the next time it is a friendly talk. Furthermore, there the observers might identify the differences among those performances and their speech and analyze that.

However, on the other hand, this activity seem to be repeated for several times at the same time. Two pupils play roles and the others observe, or vice versa. If I were a pupil, I would probably, feel a little boredom since it is not so engaging. Furthermore, as Ishahara and Cohen mentioned, pragmatics mainly focuses on authentic world, it is better to use more real materials.

What I would suggest is, firstly, adding an instructional or theoretical part for the students. I recommend to try to involve all of the students into one class and interact with them in the same class. I suppose, in the previous existing activity it is probably impossible to complete the task and to be able to communicate with all of the pupils in that way of playing role. However, if it were a concise and engaging one it would be beneficial for the teacher and the learners as well. The part that I would like to suggest is a “Chain Drill” that contains all of the learners in the class: 10-15 or 20. But this should be after a theoretical part in order to consolidate. A teacher invites the learners to make a chain not looking and seeing each other and tells a sentence to the first learner in the row. That one turns back and tell what he /she hears to the next one, thus, the chain lasts till the end and the last pupil should tell the others what h/she listened to form the other learner. Probably, it will differ from the very first one, so it will be an example of pragmatics and various understanding of the meaning. Furthermore, I would like to include authentic video materials for the learners in order to integrate all of the skills for the learners’ linguistic development. Teacher divides the class into several groups and puts a different video for each of them. The learners are to find out what level of pragmatics, formality and others they used. According to this, they will be preparing a role-play to show how much they

have understood the content. I think, these extensions will serve to improve practicality of the activity by saving time, enhancing attention span and quality of the lesson.

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